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“MY MIRACLE, SHAFRIEYA”

Life is a struggle that I must face with courage,
yet with you, the world becomes a brilliant stage.
fears that seem impossible to overcome
fade beneath the plan god has wonderfully spun.

I gaze down on your angelic face,
and my heart tightens in a warm embrace.
when troubles storm and shadows follow,
I hold you close and never let you go at all.

The months when you were small and frail,
pressures rose, and happiness seemed to fail
my world grew darkest, my heart in strife,
I feared losing you would end my life.

I prayed with every ounce of my soul,
beseeching GOD to make you whole.
to grant you life, long and bright.
so I could love and protect you with all my might.

And he answered, my miracle remains,
your presence heals my deepest pains.
created to complete my life's design,
SHAFRIEYA, forever yours, forever mine.

Through every joy, through every tear,
through every moment you grow near,
I promise to love, to guide, to be
your shelter, your strength, eternally.

SHAFRIEYA...my second born, my guiding star,
sent from above, my miracle, my heart's memoir.

